

Orineo

Plant-based plastic alternatives

Orineo creates bio-based binding agents and durable plant-based materials for replacing fossil-based products and allowing for cradle-to-cradle material-loops

Highlights of innovative features

- OriBond is a 100% plant-based 2-component thermosetting system derived from non-toxic ingredients and contains 65% non-food crop ingredients, 25% agricultural waste and 10% beet sugar derivate.
- OriBond can be used as binder in metal coating, agglomeration of granules and particles such as wood or cork and production of high-pressure laminate boards (HPL).
- In the production of wood-based panels, OriBond replaces formaldehyde and leads to water resistant boards.

A wood panel made with OriBond is 100% based on renewable resources. Therefore, it is entirely part of the carbon cycle, ideal for a Cradle-to-Cradle approach. Used panels can be reprocessed into new panels. At the end of the commercial lifecycle, if not reused, the product will not introduce toxic or persistent compounds into the environment.

Company | Ownership of innovation

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